

GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Norway

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REPORT

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<https://brage.nina.no/nina-xmlui/handle/11250/3213446>

GINAMO Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring

Genetic diversity is the foundation of biodiversity and essential for the long-term survival, adaptation, and resilience of populations, species, and entire ecosystems. While genetic diversity has long been neglected in biodiversity policy and management, the current Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) includes a strong goal and target for genetic diversity conservation and also monitoring, including with indicators and for wild species. Tools and indicators to assess and monitor genetic diversity are available but are rarely applied due to the gap in knowledge transfer between conservation science and application. GINAMO is a project of Biodiversa+, The European Biodiversity Partnership, which assesses and delivers science-based and co-designed best practices and guidelines for the use of genetic diversity indicators. This will enable the routine integration of genetic criteria and indicators into biodiversity monitoring and assessments, from policy at regional, national, and EU levels, to global conventions and obligations. A key component of GINAMO is the use of facilitated group decision-making processes to partner and co-decide from the outset with the stakeholder community. This ensures that all resources produced meet their concerns, reporting duties, and monitoring needs, and that guidelines and work flows are more likely to be adopted. Easy-to-apply, standardised and automated workflows will be co-created for assessing genetic indicators to meet national reporting obligations and to incorporate genetic diversity knowledge into nature management plans.

Main objectives

GINAMO uses existing open access genetic and non-genetic data (including Earth observation data) to best determine accurate estimates of the two genetic diversity indicators of the GBF: 1) the proportion of populations within species with an effective population size (N_e) greater than 500 ($N_e > 500$ hereafter), and 2) the proportion of populations maintained within species. To maximise the implementation and reporting of these indicators, GINAMO designs, facilitates, and scientifically evaluates co-creation processes between scientists and country stakeholders in France, Italy, Belgium, Sweden and Norway. These processes aim to collaboratively develop workflows that are scientifically sound, appropriate, compliant with policy and easy-to-implement for nature management.

Main activities

GINAMO focuses on generating best practices for assessing effective population size and evaluating genetic indicators from both DNA-based data and non-DNA (proxy) data from multiple sources. Additionally, GINAMO evaluates how satellite Earth observation data can be used to generate proxies to monitor genetic diversity. Workflows for existing and newly generated information will be standardised to provide easily accessible tools for researchers, nature managers and policy makers. GINAMO activities follow a co-creation approach under professional guidance by the European Regional Resource Center of the IUCN SSC [Conservation Planning Specialist Group](#) and with scientific evaluation by social scientists, so that methods and products are produced together by policy makers, nature managers, and scientists.

Workshop process

The workshops organised by GINAMO in collaboration with local country stakeholders serve to create input to the best practice guidelines that will be produced. In order to make these as user friendly and as relevant as possible, it is important to understand the realities in which various stakeholders operate, and to understand the challenges they experience from their perspective. The challenges identified during the workshops will inform the work of the various work packages within GINAMO, when developing the science and methods behind the use of genetic indicators.

IUCN SSC CPSG Europe designed and facilitated the country workshop processes, in line with CPSG's Principles and Steps (Appendix II), and informed by preparatory meetings with a country organising group composed of GINAMO scientists from the country and selected country stakeholders with a central role in monitoring and reporting on biodiversity.

In preparation of the workshops, a generic workflow was developed (Fig 1), that outlines the main steps that need to be taken within a country in order to be able to report genetic indicators to the CBD. This workflow was used as the basis for the discussions during the workshop.

Fig 1. The generic workflow used as a base for the workshop.

The agenda for the workshop can be found in Appendix I. Following an introduction to the GINAMO project and the genetic indicators, as well as to the workshop process and generic workflow, the active part of the workshop started. Participants first identified where in the workflow they felt their institution could have a role to play. Next, the generic workflow was divided into three parts:

1. Selection of the species to monitor and report on.
2. Data collection, indicator calculation, and storing and structuring of metadata for future reporting cycles.

3. Preparing the relevant parts of the CBD report.

For each of these three parts, the participants:

- A. Discussed their knowledge of the current situation in Norway;
- B. Identified the challenges facing them as stakeholders, or the country as a whole, in order to end up with a fully functional, and repeatable workflow that can routinely and consistently produce genetic indicators for consecutive reporting cycles to CBD.

At the end of the workshop, the participants reviewed all the challenges and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

Participants

The country organising group identified the stakeholders that would be invited to the workshop. A matrix was developed to help identify stakeholders that represented a wide variety of workflow steps, skills, roles and responsibilities, as well as geographical placement, when relevant. Not all the identified stakeholders were able to participate in the workshop, but they will all receive this report.

19 stakeholders representing various research institutes and government agencies participated. The workshop was held at the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA).

Workshop evaluation

GINAMO's social scientists will evaluate the entire co-creation process. In order to evaluate the country workshops, a survey was prepared and completed by all participants before and after the workshop. The only parts from that survey included in this report are any answers to the question: "List any stakeholders who could have made a valuable contribution but were not present at this workshop". The overall results from this evaluation will be shared at a later stage.

Workshop results

Workshop outcomes

1. An overview of the current situation in Norway with regards to: genetic monitoring and reporting, genetic and proxy data gathering and databases, already existing workflows, important stakeholder groups, scientific views regarding the use of the *Ne 500* headline indicator, etc.
2. A list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

3. A selection of those challenges for which developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

This report collects the results from the workshop in Norway, and reflects the thoughts, assumptions and knowledge of the participants at the time of the workshop, but does not claim to give the full picture of the status and challenges with regards to the reporting of genetic indicators to the CBD in Norway. The aim of this report is to inform further work by GINAMO and hopefully it will also prove to be a useful first step towards further work and collaboration within Norway, to develop and implement a national workflow.

Where in the workflow stakeholders' institutions might contribute

The workshop participants identified where in the workflow they felt their institution might have a role to play. The results are in the table below. Please note that this does not constitute an exhaustive list of stakeholders required for each workflow step.

Data on species is generated	Data about species is stored	Species list to monitor and report on	Data is collected, structured and stored	Indicators are calculated and stored	The report to the CBD is written and submitted
NIBIO	NIBIO	Miljødirektoratet	Artsdatabanken	Artsdatabanken	Miljødirektoratet
Landbruksdirektoratet	Landbruksdirektoratet	NIBIO	NMBU Norway	Nord University	Fiskeridirektoratet
Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)	Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)	Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)	Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)	Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)	Norsk institutt for naturforskning (NINA)
Nord University	Nord University	Artsdatabanken	Havforskningsinstituttet (IMR)	NTNU Trondheim	
Biofokus	Biofokus	UiA (Center for Coastal Research)	UiA (Center for Coastal Research)		
Artsdatabanken	Artsdatabanken				
Norsk Polarinstitutt	Havforskningsinstituttet (IMR)				

Havforskningsinstituttet (IMR)	UiA (Center for Coastal Research)				
Naturindex (datasource)					
Citizen Science (datasource)					

The following organisations were identified as missing from the workshop:

Conservation organizations
 Farmers association
 Fiskeridirektoratet (The Directorate of Fisheries)
 Industry organizations
 Landowners and their representatives
 More representatives from Miljødirektoratet
 Natural History Museum
 Naturvernforbundet (Friends of the Earth Norway)
 Norsk jeger og fiskerforbundet (NJFF)
 Norwegian Institute for Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) and its Norsk Gene Resource Center
 Norwegian Polar Institute
 Norwegian research institute for water and the environment (NIVA)
 Norwegian salmon rivers
 Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU)
 Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) and University Museum
 People working with agriculture
 SABIMA
 Statens naturoppsyn (SNO)
 Statsforvalterer
 University in Tromsø (UiT)
 WWF

Summary of current situation in Norway

One of the goals for the workshop was to create a common understanding of what the current situation concerning reporting to the CBD is. Therefore we asked a set of questions at the workshop to get an idea of how far Norway has come with monitoring and calculating genetic indicators.

Species list:

- Miljødirektoratet has given Artsdatabanken the mandate to decide about the species list. Artsdatabanken is coordinating the work with the Red List Assessments work that they also conduct.

Artsdatabanken has chosen four taxonomic groups to start out with: Mammals, Amphibians, Reptiles, and Butterflies. They will use proxy data to calculate genetic indicators for these groups. These are the data they have in the Red List Assessments. The plan is to calculate genetic indicators for as many of the species within these taxa as possible, not just for "important species". They will use proxy data to calculate genetic indicators, based on the data they have in the Red List Assessments.

Data is collected and stored:

- Data for the four taxonomic groups already exist.
- For the next reporting period in 2026 the genetic indicators will be collected for those.
- The Koboform is planned to be used but there is no data management plan in place yet for the calculated indicators.
- For the next reporting period in 2029, it is planned to add more species/taxonomic groups (such as birds, fish, etc).

Reporting to the CBD:

- The Miljødirektoratet has the mandate to create the report, which will then be shared with the ministry which will submit it to the CBD in 2026.
- So far only wild species are considered for the upcoming reporting period by the Miljødirektoratet.

Challenges

The workflow for reporting to CBD was divided into parts, and for each part, the workshop participants identified a list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

After identifying the challenges, the participants reviewed them all and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country. It was possible to mark a challenge as both a co-creation candidate and as a challenge that needs national work to be solved - but that is not indicated in this report. The challenges marked with (G) are the ones that were suggested for co-creation.

Data on species is generated

1. Citizen science is useful but there are challenges with it. It is difficult to determine if a species is juvenile or adult and it may be biased due to locality and how accessible the area is. Therefore this should be used mostly for occurrence validation. But it could be interesting to explore how to make use of various citizen databases for proxy data.
2. There may be a bias towards species with small population size in the data available because they are easier to calculate than large populations.

Species list to monitor and report on

1. There is still a need for a general approach to select species. Only four taxonomic groups selected so far (based on existing data). (G)
2. Limited resources and people and the time pressure to report in early 2026 are a challenge.
3. It is unclear how to deal with Svalbard. (G)
4. Climate change has changed the species composition in coastal fish and it is a bit unclear how these current changes of species composition should be dealt with in reporting.

Data is collected, structured and stored and calculating the indicators

- 1) There is a need to collaborate to include DNA data - right now only proxy based data is used to calculate indicators. Who would calculate the indicators based on genetic data?
- 2) When large data gaps exist, there are doubts about the cost effectiveness of gathering new proxy data rather than new genetic data for the calculation of genetic indicators, as fieldwork for genetic data is more straightforward than for proxy data. (G)
- 3) How to define a population with a continuous distribution and/or if there is hybridization with domesticated individuals e.g. wild reindeer, or wolves? (G)
- 4) How to treat invasive species? And how to manage them? When do you decide that this is now a population in Norway?
 - Especially a problem in the south of Norway.
- 5) How do we define populations? (G)
 - How do you deal with meta-populations - if there is a large enough gene pool between populations.
 - How do we define populations in insects?
- 6) What is the data security situation? (Who has the back-ups, where are the servers? (Came up in discussion about the KOBO form.)
- 7) There is no national infrastructure for ecological data (but there is a seed bank for domesticated plants, the veterinary institute has a collection for pathogens, and museums have collections).
- 8) How to deal with transboundary and migratory species? Are you reporting on the breeding ground?
- 9) Concerns with indicators based on proxy data: (G)
 - The N_e/N_c ratio is not the same across species/taxa. Is there a rule of thumb for each taxonomic group?
- 10) What is the correct methodology to use when using DNA for calculation of the indicators? (G)
- 11) Due to the geography of Norway there are large areas that do not have enough data to be able to calculate indicators using proxies or DNA. (G)
- 12) What is the best way to do non-invasive sampling for DNA? (G)

The report to the CBD is written and submitted

1. What is the purpose of calculating the indicators - this should be clear and should be for more than “just” the CBD. (G)
2. There should be a standard way for what CBD wants and how such reporting should look like. (G)
3. How to standardize the reporting across countries? (G)

Next steps

The GINAMO work packages will assess all challenges selected by the five countries as potentially benefiting from collaboration between GINAMO and the country stakeholders. The GINAMO work package members will assess if and how these can be incorporated into their work, and how the country stakeholders might be able to contribute. The result of this will then be reported back to the country workshop participants, together with potential next steps.

Reference materials

- Norway has committed to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and must report to the CBD using novel genetic indicators for the first time, among a large range of indicators, first in February 2026, and then periodically, typically every three to four years. Critical steps are the selection of species to report on, collecting and interpreting available data on them for the calculation of indicators, and using a reproducible approach to building successive reports. Guidelines for these steps are available:
 - CBD guidelines:
<https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/92cf/b458/18519b4c0b487bf9bfc23988/sbstta-26-inf-14-en.pdf>
 - Guidelines from the Coalition of Conservation Genetics:
<https://ccgenetics.github.io/guidelines-genetic-diversity-indicators/>
 - <https://doi.org/10.17161/bi.v18i.22332>
- Genetic diversity must be protected because it allows for the long-term persistence, resilience and adaptive potential of species.
 - policy brief: <https://g-bikegenetics.eu/en/multimedia-policy-briefs-pubs/policy-briefs>
- The genetic indicators are pragmatic and can be computed using DNA data or non-DNA proxy data.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae006>
 - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-024-01632-8>
- These indicators have been tested and validated for use in 9 countries.
 - <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2WK6T>
- National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) can be improved to include the protection of genetic diversity.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae106>

APPENDIX I: Workshop Agenda

09.00	Velkommen, introduksjon, evaluering	12.15	LUNSJ
09.40	Presentasjon av GINAMO og de genetiske indikatorene	13:15	NS/U: Å samle data, beregne og lagre informasjon
10.10	Pause	14:15	NS/U: Rapportering til CBD
10.20	Proessen for denne workshopen og for rapportering	15.00	Pause
10.35	Presentasjonsrunde / Oversikt over organisasjoner	15:15	Sortere utfordringer
11.00	Nåværende situasjon/utfordringer (NS/U): Artsliste	16.15	Neste steg, avslutning og evaluering
		17.00	SLUTT

Photo: Xiatong Cai, GINAMO

APPENDIX II: IUCN SSC CPSG

Our **mission**: to save threatened species by increasing the effectiveness of conservation efforts worldwide

Our **mantra**: every species that needs a plan is covered by an effective and implemented plan

For over 40 years we've accomplished this by:

- Providing culturally sensitive and respectful facilitation for stakeholder-inclusive conservation action planning.
- Developing and sharing innovative, interdisciplinary science-based tools and methods.
- Building capacity for species conservation planning worldwide.